

Original Article

Survival Analysis of Cancer Patients and Evaluating Efficiency of New Medication by Statistical Analysis

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Abstract

Survival analysis is a statistical method used to study the time until an event happens, like death or cancer relapse. It is especially useful in cancer research to measure how well treatments work over time. It provides the basic effectiveness of new medication and rate of survival of cancer patient. This method takes into account that not all patients experience the event during the study. Survival analysis helps us understand how different treatments affect patient outcomes and what factors influence survival. It also allows comparisons between treatments. It required the power full statistical method and time to event data. Common methods include the Kaplan-Meier estimate (which shows survival rates over time) testing helps compare survival data between groups, such as male vs. female patients or different cancer stages. Kaplan -Meier is the basic statistical method which is use to find survival rate graphically. It needs time base data of patient, the time at which cancer diagnosis till the time when event occur. A fictive data is used some of the patients are treated by old medication and other are treated by new medication and then apply the method to find which has the better effect on patient. The purpose of this article is to find the survival rate of cancer patient after taking treatment. And which treatment gives best survival rate when apply on cancer patients. Effect of treatment according to different stages of cancer. Kaplan-Meier apply after collecting different cancer patients' data from hospitals and apply statistical method by using excel and get graph. It gives better results each treatment has robust effect on survival rate of cancer patient but new medication gives better result than old medication. As per stages early stage has heigh survival rate and most of the patient become cure after treatment. Advance stage has low survival rate but get stable condition after treatment.

Keywords: *analysis of cancer patients, data of cancer patients, Kaplan-Meier estimator*

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the most common disease most of the researcher research on different types of cancer on the basis of patient's survival and factor causing cancer and many other. In this paper we discuss about survival rate on the basis of different treatment. (Kaplan & Meier, 1958). Survival analysis is a powerful statistical method used to analyze time-to-event data, especially valuable in cancer research for evaluating the effectiveness of new treatments (Le-Rademacher, J., & Wang, X. (2021)). Unlike simpler metrics like mortality rates, survival analysis considers the duration of follow-up and accounts for censored data, where the event of interest (e.g., death or relapse) hasn't occurred for all patients. (Flynn, R. (2012)). This approach provides a more understanding of treatment impact on long-term patient outcomes, offering insights into factors influencing survival and enabling comparisons between different treatment strategies. By focusing on time-to-event endpoints, survival analysis offers a powerful tool for assessing the efficacy of new cancer therapies and improving patient care. It allows researchers to measure the fraction of subjects who survive for a certain period after an intervention. (Sorlie et al., 2001).

The basic objective of this research is that doctors detect cancer early and act without delay, and people tend to have better survival outcomes (Dal Maso, L et al., (2014)). Cancer patient data can be analyzed statistically to gain insights into cancer and help doctors to detect it early and to make treatment decisions that improve patient outcomes. (Weinberg, R. A. (1996)). Statistical methods are used by research teams to

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study cancer information from prevalence numbers to risk factors to survival rates, to treatment success rates. Annual calculations determine survival rates in the research. Kaplan-Meier curves are used to study survival time influence. For this research, we have dependent variables of gender and cancer type and cancer stage and patient age. (Bland & Altman, 2004).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cancer is the most common disease all over the world. Among all breast cancer is the most rated cancer. Among all register cases most of the patient have advance stage at the time of diagnosis. It basically causes due to toxic chemical use in factory and paint chemical, traffic smoke which harm the healthy cell of body or it is inherited. This research makes data-driven decisions, improves patient care and advances cancer research. Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide, but despite great advances in medical research, effective treatment and prolonged survival are still important goals (FAIRCLOUGH, D. L. (1997)). Researchers and healthcare providers can use evidence-based decisions about treatment strategy by comparing the survival outcomes of cancer patients receiving new versus old medications. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of new medications on patient survival, and determine if the improvements justify their use in standard clinical practice. (Abbas, Z., & Rehman, S. (2018)).

Many of the newer medications offered in cancer treatment options are targeted and immune medicines designed to improve survival outcomes. (Rahman, R et al., (2014)). But the efficacy of these new medications hasn't been compared to older, well-established treatments in a range of patient populations. The problem is in deciding whether the new medications will dramatically improve the survival rate or simply add marginal benefits at higher cost. (Salas-Vega, S et al., (2017)). The problem statement of this research paper is, what are the survival outcomes of cancer patients treated with new medications versus older ones? The goal of this analysis is to help inform better treatment protocols and better patient care by providing a clear understanding of the comparative effectiveness of new and old cancer medications. (Paoletti et al., 2013). Different treatment is use to controlled abnormal growth of cancer cell. New treatments are Targeted therapy and Immunotherapy while old treatments are chemotherapy and radiation therapy. In this research we compare effect of these treatments on different type of cancer. (Winningham, M. L., (1986)).

Overall, all cancer we divide them into four main type that is carcinomas, sarcomas, leukemia and lymphoma. (Glinsky, G. V. et al., (2005)). In short carcinomas is the type of cancer which is appear when epithelial cell (which protect organ) is disturb and abnormal cancer cell growth in it. In this organ are disturb by cancer cell. Sarcomas are bone related cancer when abnormal cancer cell is grown in different bones. (Zugazagoitia, J ealt., (2016)). Leukemia is blood related cancer affecting white blood cell appear in bone marrow and badly effect on normal blood cel it has different type according to the age. Lymphoma is the type of cancer which effect immune system it is appear due to impurities in white blood cell. In this research we consider these four types of cancer and their four stages. (Allard, W. J et al., (2004)).

METHODOLOGY

This research has different strategies first of all in collecting data and sorting out the patient information according to our needs. Then secondly apply statistical tools on data to exert better information from sample data. (Cagnacci, A et al., (2025)). This research is based on the design that visits different hospitals where oncology departments are present (Clark et al. (2003)). Research the patient with different types of cancer. Read the report of the patient to get to know about their treatment. Collect a huge amount of data from hospital records with ethical consideration of patient personal information. Sample size of 1000+ will be considered for research (Ferreira & Patino, 2016). In addition, collect data by questioner by asking some useful question which help in finding better information about cancer patients. Asking age of patients at time of diagnosis, gender, stage of cancer, Type of treatment, patient is alive or not, survival time of patient if death is occurred (Kishore et al., 2010). Then change this qualitative data into numeric form by assigning some number to them, such that 1 for male 2 for female, 0 for alive and 1 for death. Then apply statistical approach for which this research use Kaplan-Meier estimator. (Miller, 1981). The Kaplan-Meier estimator is a non-parametric statistical method used to find the estimation of survival probability in a specific time interval. (Etikan, I et al., (2017)). Usually, it is applied on the data of a patient's fight with any serious disease. It deals with the time in which events of interest (mortality and relapse) occur and it will search in all samples of data.

$$S(t) = \prod_{t_i}^{t_n} \left(\frac{z_i - dt_i}{z_i} \right)$$

Where $S(t)$ is the estimated survival probability at time t .

z_i is the number of patients at risk at the start of the time t .

dt_i is the number of deaths during the time interval t .

t_i is the time where the event occurred.

Kaplan-Meier estimator is also used to compare two groups of patients to find the greater survival time between them. It generates a step wise survival graph, for visualizing the patient’s survival during a specific time interval (Kim, H. Y. (2014)).

RESULTS & FINDINGS

Table: 1 Cancer distribution by age

Count of cancer	Stages				Grand Total
	1	2	3	4	
Age					
31 - 40	14	74	146	146	380
20 - 30	22	98	44	87	251
41 - 50	12	49	86	82	229
51 - 60	2	26	25	23	76
0 - 19	11	17	35	20	83
61 - 100	9	24	37	26	96
Grand Total	70	288	373	384	1115

Table: 2 Gender wise Treatment

Count of cancer	Gender		
	1	2	Grand Total
Treatment			
chemotherapy	108	47	155
Chemotherapy, Targeted Therapy		1	1
Immunotherapy	121	75	196
Immunotherapy, Targeted Therapy	2	6	8
Radiation	49	27	76
Radiation Therapy, Immunotherapy		1	1
Radiation, Chemotherapy	145	117	262
Surgery	12	10	22
Surgery, Chemotherapy	3	9	12
Surgery, Chemotherapy, Radiation Therapy	3	4	7
Surgery, Immunotherapy		1	1
Surgery, Radiation Therapy	2		2
Surgery, Targeted Therapy	1	1	2
Surgery, Chemotherapy	39	28	67
Surgery, Radiation	25	14	39
Targeted Therapy	153	111	264
Grand Total	663	452	1115

Kaplan-Meier estimator calculation and graphs

BLOOD CANCER RESEARCH

Blood Cancer: Stage (Advance) and early stage

Report 1

Blood Cancer

Advance Stage			Early Stage		
Duration	ST (new)	ST (old)	Duration	St (new)	St (old)
0 to 0.5	1	1	0 to 1	1	1
0.5 to 1	0.97	1	1 to 3	1	0.94
1 to 3	0.85	0.79	3 to 10	0.94	0.94
3 to 5	0.47	0.37			
5 to 10	0.41	0.27			

BONE CANCER RESEARCH

Bone Cancer: Stage(Advance), and early stage
Report 2

Bone Cancer					
Advance			Early		
Duration	St(new)	St(old)	Duration	St(new)	St(old)
0 to 1	1	1	0 to 0.5	1	1
1 to3	0.76	0.25	0.5 to 1	1	0.91
3 to 5	0.36	0.06	1 to 3	1	0.83
5 to 10	0.24	0.06	3 to 5	0.93	0.83
			5 to 10	0.81	0.83

Lymphoma Research

Lymphoma: Stage (Advance),
Report 3
and

Organ Cancer Research

Organ cancer: Stage(Advance), Age17 to 60
Report 4

Lymphoma Advance Stage			Organ Advance Stage		
Duration	St (new)	St(old)	Duration	ST(new)	ST(old)
0 to 0.5	0.98	0.92	0 to 0.5	0.99351	0.97633
0.5 to 1	0.95	0.87	0.5 to 1	0.98052	0.95266
1 to 3	0.73	0.57	1 to 3	0.7987	0.61539
3 to 5	0.38	0.35	3 to 5	0.3961	0.42012
5 to 10	0.25	0.31	5 to 10	0.24026	0.36686

Interpretation

Table 1 shows the distribution of cancer stages according to age group. This shows that mostly 20 to 30 age group people suffering from cancer. Most of the patient’s diagnosis in 3 and 4 stages. 16% teenagers were suffering from cancer among those mostly diagnosis stage is 3 and 4. Age group of 20 to 30 are 31% among all those suffering from cancer. Among those mostly were diagnosis in stage 2 and 4. Age group of 30 to 40 are 20% among all those suffering from cancer. Among those mostly were diagnosis in stage 3 and 4. Age group of 40 to 50 are 17 % among all those suffering from cancer. Among those mostly were diagnosis in stage 3 and 4. Age group of 50 to 60 are 3% among all those suffering from cancer. Among those mostly were diagnosis in stage 2 and 3. Age group of 60 + are 13% among all those suffering from cancer. Among those mostly were diagnosis in stage 3 and 4.

Table 2 summary shows male and female treated by different type of medication some medications are new therapy and some are old therapy. In this table gender 1 stand for male and gender 2 stand for female. In table 2 old medication are Chemotherapy, Radiation, Surgery and new medication are Immunotherapy, Targeted Therapy. Among 663 male patients 386 were treated by old medication and 277 were treated by new medication. Among 452 female patients 256 were treated by old medication and 196 were treated by new medication.

Kaplan- Meier interpretation

Kaplan Meier use to find the survival rate of patients suffering from a disease.

Blood cancer report

In (Report 1) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from blood cancer in advance stage of age group 30 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 100% of patients survive up to 6 months of period. 97% of patients survive within 1 year of period. While 85% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 47% of patients survive more than 3 years. For old medication results shows that 100% of patients survive up to 1 year. 79% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 37% of patients survive within 3 to 5 years of period. 27% of patients survive more than 5

years. In (Report 1) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from blood cancer in early stage of age group 30 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 100% of patients survive up to 3 years of period. 94% of patients survive more than 3 years. For old medication results shows that 100% of patients survive up to 1 year. 94% of patients survive more than 1 years

Bone cancer report

In (Report 2) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from bone cancer in advance stage of age group 17 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 100% of patients survive up to 1 years of period. 76% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. While 36% of patients survive within 3 to 5 years of period. 24% of patients survive more than 5 years. For old medication results shows that 100% of patients survive up to 1 year. 25% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. Only 6% of patients survive more than 3 years. In (Report 2) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from bone cancer in early stage of age group 17 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 100% of patients survive up to 3 years of period. 93% of patients survive within 3 to 5 years of period. 81% of patients survive for more than 5 years. For old medication results shows that 100% of patients survive up to 6 months. 91% of patients survive within 1 year. 83% of patients survive more than 1 year.

lymphoma report

In (Report 3) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from lymphoma in advance stage of age group 17 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 98% of patients survive up to 6 months of period. 95% of patients survive within 1 year of period. While 73% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 38% of patients survive within 3 to 5 years of period. 25% of patients survive more than 5 years. For old medication results shows that 92% of patients survive up to 6 months. 87% of patients survive within 1 year of period. 57% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 35% of patients survive up to 3 to 5 years of period. 31% of patients survive more than 5 years.

Organ cancer report

In (Report 4) we compute survival rate of patients suffering from organ cancer in advance stage of age group 17 to 70. Compare the patients treated by new and old medication. Its results state that in new medication 99% of patients survive up to 6 months of period. 98% of patients survive within 1 year of period. While 79% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 39% of patients survive within 3 to 5 years of period. 24% of patients survive more than 5 years. For old medication results shows that 97% of patients survive up to 6 months. 95% of patients survive within 1 year of period. 61% of patients survive within 1 to 3 years of period. 42% of patients survive up to 3 to 5 years of period. 36% of patients survive more than 5 years.

Discussion

This study shows the best report about survival of different cancer patient at early and advance stages. It defined that new medication has best effect than old medication. Over all 60% of patient survive after treatment and 40% are died that is also because of late diagnosis or late age factor. Data is collected from year 2020 register cancer patient from different hospital. Over all organ cancer are mostly diagnosis then blood cancer, lymphoma and lastly bone cancer. Advance stage is more than the early stage at the time of diagnosis. As treatment added some more year to the patient age. Timely treated patient got heigh survival rate. The lungs cancer (organ cancer) report shows the better survival rate after treatment. The survival probability at 6 months from diagnosis is 64%; whereas the survival probability at 24 months is 16%. [1].

Treatment has batter effect on Cancer patient of Italy they had death rate 30% while 70% are alive after treatment [2]. Death rate in these patients by the analysis of the Kaplan-Meir survival curves. Twenty-five percent of cases died within four years, 50% within 6.9 years, and 75% within 10 years after diagnosis of disease [3]. Except treatment survival rate also depend on different psychological factor such as stress, depression, anxiety e.t.c [4]. Over the new 62 anticancer molecules introduce in 2003 and 2013 out of these 53 drugs approved by HTA agencies. 23 of these drugs increase 43% survival rate by 3 months. 6 of these drugs increase 11% survival rate by less than 3 months, and 8 of these drugs increase 15% survival rate by unknown month. Remaining increase over best alternative treatment [5,6,24]. The women suffering from

cancer their survival rate is defined by out of 38 women 32 survive in 1st month, 27 survive in 2nd month, 70% are still survive during the research so the treatment has better effect in survival [21].

Despite advancement in the treatment, the current problem to face cancer treatment is still there. Targeting single abnormal cancer cell pathways has achieved good clinical responses that have modestly affected survival in some cancers [16]. A data will be created regarding the two groups of patients. The first group will be the treated by targeted while the second group will be treated by chemo. Each group will consist of ten patients. Tables and Kaplan-Meier estimate curves which will be generated from the SPSS software will be used to analyze the data which shows that 85% patient survive for 5 months in targeted while in chemo 85% survive for 3 months. 40% patient survive for 24 months in targeted while in chemo 20% survive for 17 months [18].

Advances in cancer therapy are made by further investigation and evaluating treatment results and their effect on cancer patient the final results show 60% of patient survive after treating them [9]. For increasing the survival rate of cancer patients, needs recovery till long periods, treatment is used to overcome the disabling effects of the disease, different therapies are used for this. Different strategies are use like healthy diet exercise and timely treatment can increase the survival rate [17]. The most common cancer in the world is rated as carcinomas, lymphoma, leukemia and sarcomas. Developing countries are mainly affected by cancer. It is surveyed that 63% of people reported to death due to cancer. Developing countries manage cancer by moderate treatment that are available for cancer patient. 60% of cancer patient are get cure from cancer by new cancer treatment. Furthermore, experimental laboratories are focus on developing treatment for cancer cure [15, 12, 13, 10].

CONCLUSION

As a discussion this research shows that cancer awareness program should be held in all over the world. Everyone must go through the routine checkup every year, so if someone suffering from cancer it will be diagnosis at 1st stage. The big problem in cancer treatment is diagnosis in advance stage. Patients do not go through proper doctor treatment. People who do not know the basic symptoms they delay the checkup that will increase the stage of cancer. The survival rate increases by doing this activity. Early-stage cancer patient will recover properly after taking treatment as compare to advanced stage cancer patients. The bad side is that most of the patient come to know about cancer in advance stage which slow down the survival rate. Treatment is necessary for patients suffering from cancer. As we all knows that life and death is only in Allah's hand. But treatment can add some years to the patient's life. Both new and old medication has significant effect on survival rate of cancer patients. But new medication is more significant than old medication. New medication has low side effect than old one. New medication is better but expensive, if someone not afford expenses they must take treatment of old medication.

Everyone must take care of their health by healthy diet. Use mask at polluted places like industrial areas and transportation pollution. Healthy exercise makes healthy mechanism. Healthy life style and proper treatment will increase some years of life of patient. In future this research increases by emphasizing it on one specific cancer or specific stage, this will give more accurate precise result on survival rate. By this our understanding is improve more specifically. In next decade there will be more effected therapy is there for destroy cancer cells. In medical side effective test can be done in future, so cancer can be trigger in early stage. Its medication can grab the disease at first stage of patient. In this research we are highlight some factors of cancer patients through statistical methods. But on the other hand, there are some limitations that may affect the evaluation and conclusion of the interpretation.

The study may not apply to all the cancer patients because sample size conclusions may vary with respect to change of hospital record, region, country. So, it is not represented to all over world cancer patients. Research gives information about control of different variables like age, gender, stage of cancer. But still, it has limitations for other factors that influence survival outcomes like, environment, healthy lifestyle, pollution and their assessment may be difficult to conclude. But still, it gives more information about how different treatment effect on patient affectively.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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